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Struggles and Coping Mechanisms of Secondary Seasoned Teachers in Teaching Mathematics Using Technology

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Abstract

Given the rising integration of digital tools into educational practices in our century, it is important to comprehend how seasoned educators adjust to these developments. This qualitative research study explored the struggles and coping mechanisms of the seasoned secondary math teachers in incorporating technology into their lessons. Using phenomenological approach, fifteen seasoned math teachers from Digos City Schools Division were interviewed using the In-depth interview I to learn about their actual experiences. The results reveal the four main challenges: seasoned teachers' technological difficulties, technological resource constraint, resistance to change, curriculum integration. Teachers use a variety of strategies to address these issues, troubleshooting skills, innovative solutions, seeking help and collaborations, and continuous professional development. The report also lists the types of assistance that school administrators should provide, professional development and learning opportunities, sharing experience and peer collaboration, resource allocation and infrastructure support, and building healthy relationships with stakeholder. The results imply that with theories of social support, resilience, and stress and coping highlight the value of specialized support systems in assisting educators in successfully navigating the challenges of teaching mathematics using technology.

Keywords: *education, challenge, technology integration, phenomenology*

Introduction

Seasoned or experienced teachers who have a wealth of knowledge and additional skills in teaching mathematics confront numerous challenges as they work to cope their way through the current educational demand of teaching the subject using technology. These difficulties span a variety of areas, including absence of tools, low internet connection, low administrative support, low infrastructure, inadequate professional development. Balancing the educators' well-being and raising the standard of education they deliver requires a thorough understanding of the unique difficulties they confront.

In the global scenario, systemic problems make it difficult for seasoned teachers to integrate technology into their lesson plans. Inadequate money, infrastructure, administrative support, and professional development are among the issues facing the United States (Ghavifekr et al., 2016; Vatanartiran & Karadeniz, 2015). When it comes to the importance of technology in education, Florida educators grapple with differences between expectations and realities (Burggraaf, 2020). Inadequate educational policy, limited ICT resources, packed classrooms, and erratic power supply are among the challenges faced by Nigerian educators (Shittu & Shittu, 2015; Omare, Mwalwa, & Mutisya, 2018). These worldwide concerns draw attention to how challenging it is to modify instructional strategies for the digital era. To lower stress and boost resilience, Ketchell (2018) highlights the significance of fostering positive work environments and interpersonal relationships. This will help educators better use technology into their lessons.

In Asia, ICT integration in the classroom is met with skepticism by many seasoned educators in ASEAN (Semerci & Ayden, 2018). Their inability to stay up to date with the rapidly evolving technology landscape affects how effectively they can teach (Johnson & Smith, 2019). Insufficient training and unreliable internet connections make it more difficult for people in Malaysia to use technology effectively (Ghavifekr et al., 2016; Burggraaf, 2020; Connor & Beard, 2015). Furthermore, the potential of ICT is limited by reluctance to accept technology due to contradictory emotions and a lack of support from educational leaders (Blackwell et al., 2013; Hsu, 2016). Regular professional development workshops are suggested as a means of addressing these issues (Dai & Xia, 2020; Lian et al., 2021; Klassen et al., 2018; Mansfield & Beltman, 2019; Shields & Mullen, 2020; Mansfield et al., 2016; White & McCallum, 2020).

In the Philippines, many seasoned educators find it difficult to integrate ICT in the classroom, which can result in stress and burnout (Santos, 2021). Even with mentoring help, teachers in Candaba, Pampanga struggle with spiral progression, a lack of resources, and designing classes outside of their areas of expertise (Gonzales, 2019). Additionally, Dela Peña et al. (2022) discovered that senior teachers experience tension and anxiety when using technology. Many instructors find it challenging to adapt, even with the Department of Education's training programs (DepEd, 2020). To cope, public school teachers in General Santos City cultivate good communication and understanding, using positive experiences from their connections, passion, and duty fulfillment (Robosa et al., 2021).

Seasoned teachers face several challenges in providing quality 21st-century education, including difficulties integrating ICT due to unfamiliarity with new teaching materials, insufficient facilities, and limited time for ICT workshops (Almacin, 2023, personal interview). In Digos City Division, over 16 seasoned mathematics teachers struggle with technology use due to inadequate school facilities (Milca, 2023, personal interview). Additionally, principals encounter resistance from seasoned teachers, some of whom are reluctant to learn new technologies, while others are motivated but find it challenging (Deiparine, 2023, personal interview).

This study focused on the difficulties experienced secondary math teachers encounter and how they manage those difficulties. Experienced teachers typically participate less in seminars, workshops, and trainings related to innovative pedagogical methods, even though freshly hired teachers frequently have greater opportunity for professional growth in these areas. To further assist and empower these seasoned math teachers, the research intended to offer a thorough analysis and useful recommendations for teacher training programs, educational institutions, and legislators. It investigated the ways in which these educators employ technology in the classroom and evaluates how well professional development initiatives addressed their unique requirements. This could provide crucial information about how to enhance these programs to better support seasoned educators.

The existing research void is caused by the dearth of empirical studies that particularly address the challenges and coping mechanisms faced by secondary season instructors working in mathematics education. Most of the literature to date has focused on inexperienced teachers, failing to distinguish between the difficulties faced by educators switching from teaching other topics or grade levels to math.

Research Questions

1. What are the challenges of seasoned secondary teachers in teaching Mathematics using technology?
2. What are the coping mechanisms of seasoned secondary teachers in teaching Mathematics using technology?
3. What forms of support do the seasoned secondary teachers in Mathematics need from the school administrators?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research design. According to Moser and Korstjens (2017), qualitative research is a type of inquiry that delves into real-world issues to offer deeper insights. Specifically, this research employed a phenomenological approach. Creswell (2007) noted that phenomenology aims to distill the subjective experience of a phenomenon into a description of its universal essence. Teherani et al. (2015) described phenomenology as a research method that examines a phenomenon from the perspective of those who have lived it to understand its essence. In this study, a phenomenological approach was used to gain a deeper understanding of the challenges and coping strategies experienced by seasoned secondary teachers when teaching mathematics with technology.

Participants

The phenomenological investigation revealed the lived experiences of fifteen seasoned math teachers in Digos City Schools Division in teaching mathematics. In a qualitative research study, Additionally, Creswell (1998) suggests doing five to twenty-five interviews for a phenomenological investigation. Smaller groups make it simpler for the researcher to form deep, trusting relationships with your subjects, which promotes more organic dialogues and higher-quality data. The participants were chosen based on the following requirements.

Seasoned teachers from Digos City Division who have been teaching mathematics in the secondary level for at least 15 years; at least 50 years old. Included in this study were the seasoned mathematics teacher in the secondary level with at least 15 years of experience and are at least 50 years old.

On the other hand, not seasoned teachers who have below 15 years of experience and those that are teaching in the senior high school. Excluded those of not seasoned teachers who are under 15 years in teaching mathematics and below 50 years old willing to participate in the study. They served as information partners during the in-depth interviews.

Instruments

This qualitative study employed the Key Informant Interview (KII) as the primary data source. A person-to-person format was used to gather firsthand information. The research participants comprised male and female secondary mathematics teachers from the Digos City Division. Each of them underwent a loosely structured interview, allowing them to share their personal experiences. Semi-structured interviewing has been found to be effective for building rapport with individuals before conducting more formal interviews, especially with informants who might feel uneasy in highly structured interview settings (Bernard, 2006; Tudy, 2017). The semi-structured interviews were conducted based on an interview guide developed by the researcher. The interview questions aimed to explore the lived experiences of seasoned secondary mathematics teachers in using technology for classroom instruction.

Procedure

To better understand the phenomenon, data collection played a pivotal role in the research process. As a qualitative researcher, the researcher followed systematic procedures to ensure that the study was conducted methodically. First, he wrote a letter of permission to the Dean of the Graduate School, seeking approval to conduct the study. Secondly, he obtained approval from the Officer in Charge of the School Division Superintendent of Digos City, as the identified participants were seasoned math teachers from that area. Finally, he requested permissions from the principals of selected schools in the Digos City Division where seasoned teachers, those who had been teaching mathematics for at least 15 years and were aged 40 or older, were identified.

To collect data on the participants' lived experiences for the study, the researcher began by developing research questions. These interview questions and the study's interview guide were reviewed by experts in qualitative research and education. Data was then

gathered from in-depth interviews with individuals possessing firsthand knowledge of the phenomenon under investigation, who had been specifically selected for these interviews. All interviews were recorded and transcribed to ensure the accuracy of the responses.

As part of the data analysis process, the researcher extracted pertinent quotes from the interviews and provided a structured interpretation of them. Theorized meanings were clustered based on the similarity of ideas, which led to the formation of emergent themes by combining topics from similar clusters. The final report's writing style reflected the core struggles and coping mechanisms of seasoned secondary teachers in teaching mathematics with technology.

Data Analysis

To identify significant components associated with the importance of the themes, the material was carefully reviewed. Interviews were conducted, recorded, transcribed, and then evaluated. The phenomenological data analysis process employed the Colaizzi (1978) technique, which comprises seven steps.

First, each transcript was meticulously studied to obtain an overall understanding of the data. Second, relevant quotes from each transcript, relating to the phenomenon under investigation, were selected and transcribed on a separate sheet, complete with page and line numbers. Third, these significant statements were used to generate formulated meanings. The formulated meanings were then grouped into theme clusters, leading to emerging themes. In the fifth step, the study's results were synthesized into a comprehensive description of the phenomenon. The underlying structure of the phenomenon was then outlined in the sixth step. Finally, the findings were validated using a member-checking technique, where the researchers' descriptive results were compared with those of the study participants to ensure accuracy and consistency.

Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is one-way researchers can persuade themselves and readers that their research findings are worthy of attention (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). To complement the traditional assessment criteria of validity and reliability, Lincoln and Guba (1985) introduced the criteria of credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability to refine the idea of trustworthiness.

Credibility. Lincoln and Guba (1985) defined credibility as confidence in the accuracy and truthfulness of the research findings. This can be achieved through several methods, including prolonged engagement with participants, persistent observation, triangulation, peer debriefing, and member-checking. In this study, the researcher employed triangulation, which involves using multiple methods or data sources to verify the consistency of the findings (Tobin & Begley, 2014). The researcher did not rely solely on interview data but also conducted a comprehensive review of related research and literature to create a solid foundation for the study's problem.

Additionally, member-checking was used to ensure the transcribed text accurately captured the participants' perspectives. This involved having the transcribed interview and its interpretations reviewed by the participants who provided the data to confirm accuracy. The participants were asked to identify any errors or misinterpretations and to offer their comments or suggestions for further refinement. The signatures of participants on the interview transcripts served as a guarantee of credibility, confirming the exactness of their shared experiences as represented in the research study.

Confirmability. Confirmability means the extent to which a researcher's interpretations and findings are clearly rooted in the data, requiring clear evidence that the conclusions and interpretations stem from the collected data (Tobin & Begley, 2004). According to Guba and Lincoln (1985), confirmability is established when credibility, transferability, and dependability are all achieved. Koch (1994) proposed that researchers should include markers like the rationale for their theoretical, methodological, and analytical choices, allowing others to understand the basis for their decisions. In this study, confirmability was ensured by maintaining detailed records, including field notes, transcripts, translations, and audio recordings of all in-depth interviews with each participant. These materials were stored in archival envelopes, properly labeled, and made accessible for review by others to verify the confirmability of the study. This process provided transparency in demonstrating how the researcher's conclusions were derived from the data.

Transferability. The generalizability of an inquiry is referred to as transferability. This only applies to case-to-case transfer in qualitative research (Tobin & Begley, 2004). Researchers have no way of knowing which sites might like to transfer their findings; however, they are accountable for providing detailed descriptions so that those who want to transfer the findings can assess their transferability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In this study, sufficient details, and rich descriptions of the experiences of the school heads were ensured through in-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion and come up with similarities between situations which can be transferred into another context with enough detail and precision.

Dependability. There are four factors that determine the rigor and reliability of qualitative research, and one of them is dependability, often known as consistency (Janis. et al., 2020). The process of establishing consistency is addressed in this article via the lenses of constructivism and interpretivism. This is done because the author believes that the social reality that is observed is epistemologically counter-intuitive. The validity of this study is ensured by the fact that the personal and lived experiences of Seasoned Secondary Math Teachers in Digos City Division were used as a source for the data and information that was collected. These events served as the ground for their manifestations, both in terms of conduct and personality, which in turn served as the foundation for these testimonies and expressions. In addition to that, the researcher worked as a teacher in a public school, where he instructed students in both mathematics and connections. In this way, he had an advantage over other participants in that they can freely discuss their experiences.

Ethical Considerations

According to McLeod (2015), the study was carried out in accordance with the fundamental ethics of research, including the following: informed and voluntary consent; respect for privacy and confidentiality; risk minimization; honesty; social and cultural responsibility; research adequacy; and avoidance of conflicts of interest in the study's design and execution. It was the researcher's job to ask for permission to conduct his research in a letter to the superintendent of the Digos City School Division. He received a written confirmation from each of the individual school administrators who acted as his sources.

Confidentiality. It indicates that the researchers have an obligation to protect the identities of each participant, as well as the places where they are conducting the research and the location of the research itself. "A careful planning and conduct of the research will be set forth and taken into consideration first and even up to the presentations, interpretations, and publications of the results" (Tudy, 2017, p.105). They received advice on how to get ready for the interview while remaining discreet and anonymous. Because of this, there was no risk of a violation of confidentiality. The information and data that were gathered were then stored and protected.

Anonymity. According to Vasilateanu and Casaru (2015), this indicates that the information of each participant is contained and cannot be discriminated against by any individual to provide a guarantee of respecting the participants' right to privacy. Anonymity was achieved by hiding the individuals' real identities. To conceal their true identities from being discovered, the participants' real names were changed to pseudonyms, and they were added to codes. The researcher used pseudonyms as aliases to conceal the students' real identity. The names and signatures on the consent were covered in black permanent marker.

Additionally, keeping personal information private between the researcher and the participants was regarded as maintaining secrecy (McLeod, 2015). The privacy of the participants was protected since the data they provided was handled and reported in a way that prevented it from being associated with them specifically. The respondents' real names were not included in the transcription of their answers, and both their identities and the answers were kept secret.

Informed Consent. This applies in guaranteeing that the issues of the practicality in generating the needed data, information recording consent and collecting/using data, privacy and confidentiality, potential dangers, and advantages are taken into consideration (Harris & Atkinsons, 2015). Before scheduling the interviews or taking part in the phenomenological research process, all the participants were given the opportunity to give their informed consent. Explanations include the voluntariness of the participants' involvement, the confidentiality of their information, and their right to withdraw their participation from the study.

Results and Discussion

Struggles of Secondary Seasoned Teachers in Teaching Mathematics Using Technology

Seasoned secondary teachers frequently find it difficult to keep up with the fast-evolving technological landscape, feeling overburdened by the constant need to upgrade their knowledge and incorporate new resources into their lesson plans. They regularly struggle with issues including opposition to change, a lack of technological resources, and the difficulties of successfully incorporating technology into the curriculum, there were four themes that emerged as their challenges of the seasoned secondary teachers in mathematics in teaching mathematics namely, technological difficulties, technological resource constraint, resistance to change, and curriculum integration, as shown in able 1.

Table 1. Thematic Map of the Struggles of Seasoned Secondary Teacher in Mathematics in using Technology

<i>First Theme</i>	<i>Second Theme</i>
<i>Seasoned Teachers Technological Difficulties</i>	<i>Technological Resource Constraint</i>
Lack of Knowledge about the technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of skills in technology • Hard time in using the applications due to lack of knowledge • Teachers don't have knowledge of that certain application since they don't have it in college 	Limited Access to technological devices <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of modern facilities to create the lesson to be taught • Resources are not available in the classroom • Limited to powerpoint presentations, downloaded videos, offline graphing calculated, and google searches by group
Complexity of using technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard time in following the steps in using the technology • Hard time in manipulating the technology • Issues especially the knowledge and operation of highly or advance feature of technology 	Limited Technical Support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow to non-existent internet in the classroom to use to technology • Lack of basic classroom facilities such as electricity • Other classrooms don't have internet connections to use for the applications
Fear in using technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fear of making mistakes in using technology 	Inadequate trainings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seminars are not enough toto absorbed on how to use technology

- Afraid in using technologies that the files might lost or carries virus
- Anxiety in using technology de to lack of knowledge of the applications
- Step-by-step in manipulating the technology during tl seminars
- Seminar that is uncleared to its objectives

<i>Third Theme</i> <i>Resistance to Change</i>	<i>Fourth Theme</i> <i>Curriculum Integration</i>
<p>Comfort of traditional methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional method is still the easiest way of classroom instructions for the teachers • Difficulties in using ICT instead used the old methods • Switching to 21st skills technology is difficult <p>Perceived vales and relevance of the lesson</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties to follow a class that used a lot of technology • Hard of finding an application that fits to the lessons or competencies • Absence of contemporary resources to develop the lessons that need to be taught and the locations in which that ought to be delivered <p>Concern about students' engagement and learning outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Given the design of the classrooms in public schools, we are unable to put into practice • Given the reality of the classrooms in the public we cannot implement and assess the engagement of the students 	<p>Integration challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulties in integration of due to availability of technologies and facilities that we need to use • Difficulties in integrating math curricula due to manipulating the technologies due to her age • Difficulty in coping with new trend in using technology particularly in making learning materials <p>Difficulty of integrating technology to the lesson</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard to find an application that will fit to the learning competencies • It is hard for me to absorbed the knowledge in using the technology • Lack of knowledge and experience on how to use technology <p>Time constraint</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It requires more hours to prepare • Continuous to change from time to time • Needs two to three days for me to prepare

Technological Difficulties. Technology integration in education is growing in popularity and opening new teaching and learning opportunities. All the same, adopting technology might be extremely difficult for seasoned teachers who are responsible for teaching mathematical ideas. As pillars of the educational system, these seasoned teachers frequently struggle with the challenges of integrating digital tools into their teaching methods. As they attempt to fully utilize technology in mathematics instruction, experienced teachers encounter a variety of difficulties, from figuring out constantly changing software to guaranteeing equal access to resources. Seasoned secondary math teachers discussed the challenges that they face as well as the difficulties associated with lack of knowledge about the technology into math instruction. KII 10 said,

"Kulang dyud me sa mga pagsabot anang technology sir labi na sa Microsoft windows and photoshop, lisod kayo siya sa amoa part kay sa amoa edad lisod na makahinum dum kung unsaon usahay makalimot na dyud" (Transcript 10, Page 1, Line 13-15).

"I lack the understanding of technology, sir, especially in Microsoft windows and photoshop, it is difficult for us because at our age, it is difficult to remember how to sometimes forget."

Like what the other seasoned secondary math's teacher had encountered difficulties in using the applications due to lack of knowledge, KII 12 remarked,

"Diba naa man mga apps ana sa Math noh, na lisod siya gamiton kay karun pa na encounter ba unya si teacher kulang pa sa knowledge about sa technology" (Transcript 12, Page 1, Line 23-25).

(There are applications in mathematics that are difficult to use because the teacher is still lack of knowledge).

The thoughts were also expressed by another experienced teacher shared her experience in using technology, hence in their time they don't have a specific subject about ICT, KII 4 noted,

"Lisod dyud ko kay wala dyud ko knowledge, pag school naku wala pa dyud na ang mga laptop og uban pa na applications sa math" (Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 14-17).

(Its hard for me to follow the steps for it to fit in, especially in the learning competencies on that week)

Though it opens new avenues for learning, integrating technology into the classroom may be very difficult for seasoned educators, particularly when it comes to teaching math. Ensuring fair access to technology resources and managing continually evolving software are challenges that these educators face. A lot of people point to a lack of technology expertise and training. Some even mention having trouble utilizing apps for arithmetic and Photoshop and mentioning that their own schooling included little to no ICT courses.

Teachers also have complexity of using technology. Seasoned Secondary teachers also shared experiences about hard time in following the steps in using technology. K15 said,

“Lisod sa pagsubay sa mga steps kung unsaon mahimo dyud siya og mahaum ana labi na sa learning competencies ana na semanaha” (Transcript 15, Page 1, Line 17-19).

(It’s hard for me to follow the steps for it to fit in, especially in the learning competencies on that week)

Another secondary Seasoned teacher also shared on having a hard time manipulating the technology. KII 6 said,

“naglisod ko sa pag gamit sa technology sa akua klase mao ng dili kayo naku siya ginagamit” (Transcript 6, Page 1, Line 13-15)

(Hard time in manipulating the technology especially in my class so I don’t use it usually)

Seasoned teacher also has an issue especially the knowledge and operations of highly or advance features of technology. KII 9 said,

“We have issues especially the knowledge on the operation of highly or advanced features technology. Specifically, the cost of this technology. And it keeps changing from time-to-time which cost lots of time and efforts and even money”. (Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 12-14).

Seasoned secondary teachers encounter challenges while utilizing technology, frequently finding it difficult to follow instructions and incorporate it into weekly learning objectives. Many find it difficult to use technology in the classroom, which results in infrequent utilization. These educators also mention difficulties in comprehending the latest updates and enhanced capabilities, which call for a substantial investment of time, money, and effort.

Fear of using technology was also shared by the seasoned secondary teachers particular in making a mistake in using technology. KII 2 said,

“Mahadlok lang dyud ko pag nay mahilabtan basig mawala ang files na akoang ginabuhat” (Transcript 2, Page 1, Line 14-15).

(I am afraid that I make mistakes and my files will be lost)

Secondary seasoned teacher is also afraid in using technologies that the files might lost or carries virus same sentiments with other seasoned teachers. KII 9 said,

“I am afraid manipulating some technologies. I’m afraid that the files might lost, or I have some applications that carry virus that will affect my laptop.” (Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 20-21).

Anxiety in using technology due to lack of knowledge of the applications was also shared by KII 3,

“Makulbaan dyud ko labi na sa pag gamit sa applications, maglisod ko labi na ma mali naku og tuplok labi na sa amoang edad, unya pagbalik nimu mawala” (Transcript 3, Page 1, Line 17-18).

(I feel nervous every time I used applications, at my age I also have hard time especially if I accidentally click something wrong happened)

Seasoned secondary teachers express concern about utilizing technology incorrectly, especially when it comes to the possibility of losing files. Their reluctance to use technology is exacerbated by worries about infections and a lack of application skills. Due in large part to their advanced age and expertise with digital tools, many teachers experience anxiety and struggle with the possible implications of unintentional errors.

Technological Resource Constrain. Technology integration has become a key component of successful teaching strategies in today's educational environment, providing creative approaches to increase student engagement and improve learning results. But for experienced educators entrusted with teaching Mathematics, antiquated technology presents a major obstacle to efficient use of technology in the classroom. These teachers are highly skilled educators with a plethora of knowledge and experience, but they are frequently limited by outdated gear and infrastructure, which makes it harder for them to fully utilize digital resources. The present introduction establishes the groundwork for an examination of the challenges and flexible tactics utilized by seasoned secondary educators in addressing the constraints imposed by antiquated technology within the context of teaching mathematics. Lack of modern facilities to create the lesson be taught is one of struggles that the seasoned teachers encountered. Seasoned Secondary teacher KII 8 said:

“The lack of modern facilities to create the lessons to be taught, and the venue where we should present the said lesson. Kay ang classroom daghan dyud og kulang na mga gamit ultimo kuryente wala gani me” (Transcript 8, Page 1, Line 19-20).

(The lack of modern facilities to create the lessons to be taught and the venue where we should present the said lesson. The classrooms that we have no equipment to be used and even the source of electricity is not available)

Other participants also shared that the resources are not available in the classroom. Seasoned teacher KII 3 said,

"We are limited in our resources. We don't have technologies to use inside the classroom, so it is really difficult for me" (Transcript 3, Page 1, Line 14-15).

Some seasoned secondary teachers shared that one of the common problems they encountered as a public teachers teaching mathematics using technology is the facilities emphasizing that they are limited to PowerPoint presentations, and downloaded videos. KII 2 said,

"We are limited to PowerPoint presentations, downloaded videos, offline graphic calculated, and google searches by group. Pabalik balik rami ani na instructional materials kay mao raman available." (Transcript 2, Page 1, Line 19-21).

(We are limited to PowerPoint presentations, downloaded videos, offline graphic calculated and google searches by group. We keep repeating the instructional materials that is only available)

The old infrastructure and equipment present a huge hurdle for seasoned math teachers when it comes to integrating technology. They frequently lack up-to-date infrastructure, appropriate teaching materials, and dependable internet access, which makes it challenging to employ digital technologies efficiently. As such, their access to sophisticated teaching resources is restricted to PowerPoint presentations and downloadable movies, which limits their capacity to effectively engage students and improve learning results.

Some participants shared that they have limited technical support in the school, due to non-existent internet in the classroom to use technology. KII 2 said,

"Slow to nonexistent of internet. Ang eskwelahan namu wala man dyud internet connections so dili dyud me makagamit anang applications para ana na lesson." (Transcript 2, Page 1, Line 24-24).

(Slow to nonexistent of internet. The school had no internet connections so we cannot utilize the applications for that certain lesson.)

Some secondary seasoned teachers also shared that the lack of basic classroom facilities such as electricity is one of the problems in their classrooms. KII 7 said:

"Sa classroom namu diri sa national makita dyud nimu na ang classroom mismo dili pa dyud andam. Problem namu we have lack of basic classroom facilities such as electricity. Katong nag held gani ang Digos og RSPC dayun gi gamit ni diri wala tauwn kuryente ang ubang room". (Transcript 7, Page 1, Line 11-15)

(In our classroom here in National you will see that our classroom is not ready. The problem here is we have lack of basic classroom facilities such as electricity. Remember when Digos held RSPC and our school used as one of the billeting quarter some rooms don't have an electricity).

Other seasoned secondary teachers shared that other classrooms do not have internet connections to use for the apps. KII 3 said,

"Poor internet connections. I would love to explore, download, and incorporate apps, videos online activities in my math teaching but this would be impractical since there is no consistent internet connections inside the classroom, especially in the classroom." (Transcript 3, Page 1, Line 14-16)

The lack of adequate technical assistance and inadequate internet access in classrooms pose major challenges for seasoned secondary teachers when implementing educational technology. Moreover, a lot of classrooms are devoid of essential amenities like power, which makes it challenging to establish a comfortable learning atmosphere. Due to these problems, educators are unable to properly investigate and integrate online activities, apps, and digital resources into their math lessons.

Inadequate trainings are one of the issues and struggles by the seasoned secondary teachers. Seminars are not enough to absorb on how to use the technology. KII 1 said,

"Gipaseminars mi, pero dili kayo ma-absorb kay days raman, maglisod dyud gihapon labaw na sa amoang edad na dili man tawun na makuha sa 3 ka adlaw lang na seminar naglisod man gani og gamit na cellphone na touchscreen kana pa kaya" (Transcript 1, Page 1, Line 24-26).

(We undergo seminars, but it is hard to absorbed in just days, it's difficult specially in our age we cannot absorbed the topics in just 3 days, we really have some hard time before using touchscreen how much more the applications).

Step-by-step in manipulating the technology during the seminars are one of the sentiments by the seasoned secondary teachers. KII 4 said,

"Okay ra unta na dali ra kayo sa pagseminar, itudlo unta mano-mano, kay ilahang gina tudlo theory raman kaayo wala man kayo pag applied dili makuha sa pag sulti lang sa amoa dayun kami nag lingcod lang" (Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 12-13).

(It's okay that would be easy to have a seminar that we are taught step-by-step coz their more in theories we have not taught how to be used or applied, we cannot get in simply by telling us while we are seating)

Seasoned secondary teachers also shared that there are seminars that is unclear to its objectives. KII 5 said,

“Seminar na walay klaro ng seminar, naa silay ana, pero pag -abot didto dili kayo matudlo kay walay materials,, mag yaw-yaw ra ang trainer igo ra gibasa ang iyahang gitudlo.” (Transcript 5, Page 1, Line 15-19).

“Seminar that is unclear to its objectives, they have like that, but when you're in the classroom you cannot use it because you don't have the materials, some trainer will just talk and just read the modules then no applications.”

Seasoned secondary teachers find it difficult to receive comprehensive training on technology use because the brief seminars don't allow them to fully comprehend the topic, especially considering their advanced age and expertise with digital technologies. Rather than theory-heavy sessions that don't translate well into practical application, they convey the desire for hands-on, step-by-step education. Furthermore, a few seminars are devoid of essential materials and objectives, which makes it difficult for teachers to put what they've learned into practice.

Resistance to Change. Technology integration is becoming more and more necessary in the ever-changing educational landscape because it opens new possibilities for instruction and learning. But adopting new technology can occasionally encounter pushback from seasoned Mathematics teachers. Several things contribute to this aversion to change, such as comfort with conventional teaching techniques, worries about technical competence, and anxieties about upsetting established classroom patterns. Even while they understand the potential advantages of using technology in the classroom, many seasoned teachers may be reluctant to fully adopt new resources out of a fear of the unknown and a preference for the security of tried-and-true methods. This introduction lays the groundwork for an examination of the difficulties and coping strategies faced by seasoned secondary educators when attempting to teach mathematics in the context of technological resistance to change. Seasoned secondary teacher shared that traditional method is still the easiest way of classroom instructions for teachers. KII 2 said,

“Traditional teaching is still the easiest way of classroom instruction for the teachers specially if you find it difficult to use the technology you go back to the method wherein you are mastered” (Transcript 2, Page 2, Line 30-31).

The Secondary Seasoned Teachers in Mathematics had similar feelings about difficulties in using ICT instead used the old methods. KII 6 said:

“We can always go back to the old school method, what is important we can impart acquired knowledge to our recipients. Kay ang important na tudlo na nimu nahatag nimu ang dapat sa mga bata bisag kulang og materials para ana.” (Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 34-35)

(We can always go back to the old method, what is important we can impart acquired knowledge to our recipients. What is important we taught what is necessary and what must the learners to have despite of the lack of materials)

The similar experience was also experienced by some participants that switching to 21st skills technology is difficult. KII 4 expressed,

“I am used to traditional teaching methods; it takes me long time to effectively incorporate technology into my math curriculum.” (Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 26-27).

Due to their familiarity with conventional teaching techniques, apprehensions regarding their technical proficiency, and apprehension about upsetting established classroom routines, seasoned math teachers frequently oppose the use of new technologies. Many educators still favor the familiarity and ease of use of traditional instruction even when they are aware of the potential advantages of technology. This reluctance to change might be caused by a fear of the unknown and a desire for tried-and-true methods, which makes people stick to traditional teaching methods instead of completely adopting new technologies.

Secondary Seasoned Teachers perceived values and relevance of the lesson, difficulties to follow a class that used a lot of technology. KII 8 also shared:

“Naglisod ko sa pag gamit sa technology sa akua klase mao ng dili kaayo naku siya ginagamit” (Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 30-31).

(It's hard to use technology in my class that is why I don't use it often)

Seasoned Secondary teachers had some hard time of finding an application that fits to the lesson or competencies. KII 7 said,

“Lisod mangita og applications na mahaum sa imuhang gitudlo labi na sa situations sa inyuhang eskwelahan na daghan kaayo og kulang na materials” (Transcript 7, Page 1, Line 34-36).

(It's difficult to find an application that could fit to the lessons or competencies specially in the situations of the school that lack of materials)

Absence of contemporary resources to develop the lessons that need to be taught and the locations in which they ought to be delivered. KII 6 said,

“Akoang kuanon usahay pagkulang dyud mga materials labi na sa amoang lugar mangita ko og pamaagi na ma deliver dyud ang competencies ana” (Transcript 6, Page 1, Line 18-20)

(If the absence of contemporary resources to develop a lesson I look for an alternative way specially in or locations for me to deliver the competencies)

Seasoned secondary teachers frequently find it challenging to integrate technology into their lessons because of what they perceive to be obstacles and difficulty in locating appropriate resources or programs that match the learning objectives and competencies. Their inability to provide the necessary content in an efficient manner is further complicated by the absence of modern tools and resources in their educational environments. As a result, some educators choose to employ alternative techniques to guarantee that students learn the material and achieve proficiency instead of utilizing technology heavily in the classroom.

Seasoned secondary teachers also concern about students' engagement and learning outcomes, given the design of the classroom in public schools, we are unable to put into practice. KII 6 said,

“Specially using technology with the current situations of the school, lisod kaayo siya mugamit anang applications para sa imuhang lessons.” (Transcript 6, Page 1, Line 11-12)

(Specially using technology with the current situations of the school it's hard to use the application for the lesson)

Given the reality of the classrooms in the public we cannot implement and assess the engagement of the students. KII 7 said:

“We cannot implement it given the reality of the classrooms we have in the public schools and kay dili pud nato ma assess dyud ang engagement sa mga bata” (Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 27-28)

(We cannot implement it given the reality of the classrooms we have in the public schools, and we cannot assess the engagement of the students)

Due to restrictions in public school environments that make it difficult for them to engage pupils and evaluate learning objectives, seasoned secondary teachers voice worries about using technology in the classroom. Accurately assessing student participation and implementing technology-based lessons are difficult in public schools given the current setup. Consequently, to optimize student learning experiences and outcomes, teachers encounter challenges while attempting to effectively utilize technological resources.

Curriculum Integration. Experienced secondary teachers may find it more difficult to incorporate technology into the mathematics curriculum since they are less accustomed to using digital tools than they are to using traditional ones. It is essential to offer structured professional development that emphasizes practical, hands-on training with technology, such as interactive whiteboards, mathematical software, and online learning platforms, to these educators as they work to adapt. Teachers can exchange techniques, thoughts, and triumphs via collaborative planning sessions and peer mentoring, two support mechanisms that can be built to address their challenges. Schools can also create a welcoming atmosphere that promotes experimentation and recognizes the learning curve that comes with implementing new technology. Seasoned secondary teachers can be given the tools they need to get over their early obstacles and develop a culture of ongoing learning and adaptation, which will allow them to improve their methods and involve students in more engaging and dynamic ways. The difficulties in integration of due to availability off technologies and facilities that we need to use. KII 5 said,

“Lack of facilities and outdated technologies mao na problema namu mo samot kalisod sa amoang sitwasyon.” (Transcript 5, Page 2, Line 27-28)

(lack of facilities and outdated technologies and its more difficult with our situations)

Difficulties in integrating in math curricula due to manipulating the technologies due to her age. KII 9 also shared that,

“Kana dyud pag gamit sa technology dili biya ko sanay parehas sa akoang edad nuh para dali mao ng akoang ingnun kailangan tun an pa naku (Transcript 14, Page 1, Line 15-16).

(difficulties in integrating technology in my age I need to learn how to use the applications)

Difficulties in coping with new trend in using technology particularly in making materials. KII 15 also shared its sentiments said,

“I have difficulty coping with the new trend in using technology, particularly in making learning materials.” (Transcript 3, Page 1, Line 19).

Teachers already have a difficult time integrating technology because of outdated technologies and limited facilities. Further impeding the inclusion of digital technologies into math courses are age-related difficulties associated to technological manipulation. The difficulty teachers have adjusting to new technological trends, especially when it comes to developing lesson plans, highlights the continuous difficulties in keeping up with technological changes.

Difficulty integrating technology to the lesson, one of that is hard to find an application that will fit to the learning competencies. KII 15 said,

“Naay mga competencies na lisod pero mag-depende dyud sa competencies, parehas ana ma view lang nila pero lage dili kayo magamit

nila.” (Transcript 1, Page 1, Line 11-12).

(There are some competencies that are difficult but still it will depend on the learning competencies, they can only view but they cannot use it.)

Seasoned Secondary teachers had a hard time in absorbed the knowledge in using technology. KII 13 said,

“It’s hard for me to absorbed the knowledge in using the technology kana gud mag lisod ka unsaon nimu pag integrate sa imuhang lesson na ma integrate lang dyud na siya”(Transcript 13, Page 1, Line 20-22)

(It’s hard for me to absorb the knowledge in using technology, incorporating my lesson to the technology in my lesson that will really integrate)

Lack of experience and knowledge on how to use technology was also shared by the seasoned secondary teacher. KII 14 said,

“Lack dyud ko sa experience og knowledge sa paggamit wala biya me ana katong college pa me” (Transcript 14, Page 1, Line 17-18)

(Lack of knowledge and experience on how use the technology since we don’t have it during our college)

Finding applications that match learning objectives and assimilating technology-related knowledge and skills are the main causes of difficulty incorporating technology into classes. Experienced secondary educators also deal with challenges arising from insufficient exposure to technology during their college education, which they blame for their lack of experience and understanding in this area. These challenges make it more difficult for them to use technology into their lesson plans and involve their pupils in worthwhile learning activities.

Some of the participants shared that using technology takes time. It requires more hours to prepare. KII 2 said,

“Inclusion of technology in the instructions become more difficult and it requires more hours to prepare (Transcript 2, Page 2, Line 32-33).

Seasoned secondary teachers also shared its difficulties in teaching mathematics using technology specially the technology continuous to change from time to time, KII said:

“It keeps changing from time-to-time which costs lots of time and efforts and even money” (Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 15-16)

It needs two to three days for them to prepare the materials that they need to use in the lesson. KII 4 said,

“I get everything ready two or three days before the discussions kay kung dili naku na buhaton mag lisod ko dili man ko kabalo biya ana na applications labi nan aa may observed sa imuha” (Transcript 4, Page 2, Line 32-33)

(I get everything ready two or three days before the discussions if I won’t do that it would be more difficult coz, I really don’t know how to manipulate the applications specially if there is an observation)

The participants emphasized that, to assure efficacy, integrating technology into training requires substantial planning, which frequently takes extra hours. Experienced secondary educators encounter constant difficulties when integrating technology into mathematics instruction because of the fast-evolving nature of this field, which necessitates constant time, energy, and financial commitment. Teachers frequently need two to three days to ensure that all the resources for their classes utilizing technology are ready for successful instruction, especially when they are going to be observed or evaluated.

Due to the quick evolution of educational tech tools, seasoned secondary math teachers frequently find it difficult to incorporate technology into their lessons. Their enthusiasm to adopt new technology is tempered by several challenges, including software flaws, old equipment, and technological faults that make the shift from traditional teaching techniques difficult. Another important factor is resistance to change; even when they are aware of the possible advantages of technology, some instructors are still reluctant to break away from traditional methods.

These difficulties are made worse by insufficient infrastructure, which emphasizes the need for specialized assistance and instruction to promote the use of technology in the classroom. These instructors' accounts demonstrate a thorough comprehension of the challenges associated with integrating technology into the classroom as well as a strong willingness to improve and develop their instructional strategies. It is imperative to offer individualized, phased support and development opportunities that are tailored to the special requirements of seasoned instructors to effectively address these problems and create an environment that uses technology to enhance mathematical learning results.

Coping Mechanisms of the Seasoned Secondary Teachers in teaching Mathematics using Technology.

Seasoned secondary teachers utilize many coping strategies to effectively manage the obstacles associated with incorporating technology into math education. These educators use a variety of tactics to improve their teaching practices in the digital age, such as looking for professional development opportunities, working with peers, and coming up with innovative lesson plans. These coping mechanisms can be grouped into four emerging themes: troubleshooting skills, innovative solutions, seeking help and collaborations,

and continuous professional development. That can be shown in Table 2.

Table 2. *Thematic map of the coping mechanisms of seasoned secondary teachers in teaching mathematics using technology*

<i>First Theme</i>	<i>Second Theme</i>
<i>Troubleshooting Skills</i>	<i>Innovative Solutions</i>
Familiarity with educational technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study technology that you will use for the lesson • Familiarity of the technology specially the use of graphic calculator in solving mathematical problems • Step-by-step understanding on how to use the applications 	Teachers to develop homemade or low-cost technological solutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modify the use of technology for students' exposure to it • Finding some alternative solutions in making instructional materials if there is a problem with technology • Provides a use game-based learning to students
Online tutorial of using the technology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch video tutorials on how to use specific computer applications • Research on youtube about the applications • Searching instructional materials that used technology in the internet 	Building resourceful culture <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extrapolate ways to deliver the learning competencies • Go back to traditional methods like boards and chalk and indigenous materials • Use of bitaymax and pebbles in delivering lessons
Accessing technical supports <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asking help from my co-teachers in times of difficulties in using technology • Seeking support from the IT experts in our departments • Approach ICT coordinator if difficulties arise regarding the application 	Innovative solutions in delivering lessons to the students <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used offline learning materials such as textbooks, workbooks, and printed worksheets • Strategy or finding ways to deliver lessons following the book • Innovate activities without the use of technology or contextualize materials or activities
<i>Third Theme</i>	<i>Fourth Theme</i>
<i>Seeking Help and Collaborations</i>	<i>Continuous Professional Development</i>
Seeking mentorship and guidance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LAC session every month provided by the LAC coordinator • Ask supports from the colleagues every time they encounter difficulties on certain apps • Seek supports from our colleagues and experts by collaborations meetings and conferences 	Need for ongoing professional development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never be afraid to seek for assistance when I need it • Having a peer tutoring sessions • Need for ongoing professional development
Recognizing the need for assistance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tapped somebody who is an expert technologically in doing • Gathered some ideas on how to make the lesson easy and presentable • Asked questions to our IT whenever needed help with technology 	Fostering collaborative learning communities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requesting assistance from my other educators and going to seminar • Helping one another through challenges thru our master teachers as mentor • Assistance from other educators with ICT knowledge
Overcoming Resistance to change <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asking my co-teacher for help repeatedly • Asking my co-teachers on how to manipulate the technology • Asking assistance for my colleagues 	Building technological proficiency and confidence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practice the applications two or three days before the discussions • Doing some research in making lessons simplified • Visit youtube and watch online tutorial on how to use the applications

Troubleshooting Skills. Seasoned secondary educators have always looked for someone to help them overcome the challenges they faced when integrating technology into the math classroom. Familiarity with Educational Technology. Study the technology that they will use for the lesson. KII 4 said,

“Syempre kanang pag operate naku sa applications kay kailangan pa biya naku siya studyhan nuh sa akoang kuan lesson” (Transcript 14, Page 1, Line 20-21)

(Particularly how to operate the applications I need to study that I used for the lesson)

Some participants also shared that familiarity of the technology specially the use of graphic calculator in solving mathematical problems

is one of the coping mechanisms that they have. KII 11 said,

“Familiarity of the technology specially the graphic calculator in solving mathematics kay lsoido biya siya gamiton pag dili ka kabalo mag lisod og magsakit imuhang ulo so mao ng timan an dyud nimu unnsaon pag gamit” (Transcript 11, Page 2, Line 31-34).

(Familiarity of the technology specially the graphic calculator in solving mathematics because it is difficult to used if you don't know it will be hard and you will have a headache analyzing how to use.)

Other seasoned secondary teachers who teach mathematics using technology also shared their experiences on how to cope with their struggles. They follow a step-by-step understanding of how to use the applications. KII 9 said,

“kanang ginatudluan me sa amoang kauban man sir gina follow lang namu ang step-by-step procedure na ilahang gitudlo sa amoa para mas masabtan dyud namu unnsaon pag gamitang application” (Transcript 9, Page 1, Line 26-28).

(since we're taught by our colleague's sir so we follow the step-by-step procedures that they taught us for me to understand how to manipulate and use the application)

Seasoned secondary teachers deal with the difficulties of incorporating technology into math instruction by employing a variety of coping strategies. These include researching the equipment they intend to use in the classroom, becoming comfortable with tools like visual calculators to facilitate problem-solving, and adhering to colleagues' step-by-step instructions to improve comprehension and application utilization. Teachers want to overcome technology obstacles and provide successful math courses in the digital age by actively implementing these tactics.

Online tutorials of using the technology are one of the coping mechanisms of the seasoned secondary teachers in teaching mathematics using technology, like watching video tutorials on how to use specific computer applications. KII 7said,

“Watch video tutorials on how to use specific computer applications mao na akoa solusyon sir labi na need naku na gamiton kay obserbaran ko sa amoa master teacher” (Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 32-33)

(Watch video tutorial on how to use specific computer application that is my solution sir specially if you need to use it because you will be observed by your master teachers)

Other seasoned secondary teachers also research on youtube about the applications. KII 3 said,

“I usually research on youtube about the applications” (Transcript 3, Page 2 Line 30)

Searching instructional materials that use technology in the internet. KII 5 said:

“Searching instructional materials that used technology on the internet” (Transcript 5, Page 2, Line 32-33)

Seasoned secondary teachers use a variety of coping strategies to improve their ability to use technology to teach mathematics. Among these tactics is the use of online tutorials, especially video tutorials on certain computer software, to acquire the knowledge and abilities required for efficient teaching. Educators can also access technologically infused educational materials by searching the internet and YouTube, giving them the opportunity to enhance their teaching methods and adjust to the needs of contemporary education.

Accessing technical support, particularly asking help from co-teachers in time of difficulties in using technology is one of the copings of the seasoned teacher. KII 10 said:

“Ask help from my co-teachers who are experts in some areas for me to assist me with the problem with the technology” (Transcript 10, Page 2, Line 42)

Seeking support from the IT experts in their departments is one of the solutions of the seasoned secondary teachers. KII 2 said,

“I asked questions to our IT whenever I needed help with technology, since our IT is very approachable and knowledgeable with regard to the technology” (Transcript 2, Page 2, Line 43)

Seasoned secondary teachers approach ICT coordinator if difficulties arise regarding the applications. KII 15 shared,

“mag-approach ko pag dili ko kabalo,mo adto ko sa akoang ICT coordinator especially pag ili na gyud makaya unnsaon pag gamit sa applications”(Transcript 15,Page 2, Line 34-35)

(approach my ICT coordinator if difficulties will arise regarding the applications that I use)

Seasoned secondary teachers utilize many assistance mechanisms to surmount technical obstacles when instructing math classes. When they run into trouble with a particular application, they talk to IT specialists in their departments, ask other co-teachers who are more experienced in that area, and ask ICT coordinators for advice. Educators can improve their teaching skills in the digital age and successfully address technical challenges by utilizing these support networks.

Innovative Solutions. Experienced Mathematics teachers frequently find that their teaching career is defined by an ongoing search for

creative and efficient ways to solve problems. In a time when technology is ingrained in many facets of education, these seasoned teachers have difficulties when incorporating technology into their lesson plans. Experienced teachers are skilled problem solvers who are always looking for ways to improve mathematics instruction, whether it is through adjusting teaching strategies or battling with complicated software. This introduction lays the groundwork for an investigation into how seasoned secondary educators negotiate the complex process of identifying problems and coming up with creative solutions while utilizing technology to enhance their pupils' math's education.

Modifying the use of technology for students' exposures. KII 7 said,

"Modify the use of technology for students' exposure to it, para pud dili mag salig sa technology kay ang availability pud sa technology imuhang basihan" (Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 32-33)

(Modify the use of technology for students exposure to it, for you not to be dependent of technology and if the technology is not also available)

Finding some alternative solutions in making instructional materials if there is a problem with technology. KII 13,

"Finding some alternatives, usahay mubalik pero mas gwapo naman gud ang mag research pero naa dyud time mubalik ka sir" (Transcript 13, Page 1, Line 35-36)

(Finding some alternatives, sometimes we go back to traditional. It's good to do research but there are times that you need to go back to the basic)

Seasoned secondary teachers also provides a use of game-based learning to students. KII 13 said,

"I use game-based learning to the student's kung dili dyud available ang technology or applications na gamitonon" (Transcript 9, Page 2, Line 36-37)

(I use game-based learning to the students if the technology or applications is not available)

This introduction lays the groundwork for investigating how seasoned secondary teachers overcome obstacles and come up with creative fixes to improve math instruction using technology. Modifying students' usage of technology to control their dependence on it, coming up with alternate methods for teaching materials, and utilizing game-based learning in place of technology or application-specific training are some strategies. Despite technology limitations, teachers maintain effective mathematics instruction by accepting varied teaching styles and modifying their methods accordingly.

Building resourceful culture through extrapolate ways to deliver the learning competencies. KII 2 said,

"Akoang kuanon usahay muadto ta sa mga tinamban na pamaagi, mangita dyud og pamaagi na madeliver dyud ang competencies" (Transcript 2, Page 2, Line 38-40).

(Extrapolate ways sometimes, look for alternative ways to deliver the competencies)

Secondary seasoned teachers go back to traditional methods like board and chalks and indigenous materials. KII 10 said,

"We used the traditional like boards and chalks and indigenous materials or materials that can be used around" (Transcript 10, Page 2, Line 37-38)

Others seasoned secondary teachers used "bitaymax" and pebbles in delivering the lessons. KII 1 said,

"Pebbles og bitaymax akoang gamit pagdeliver sa lesson pag wala dyud og mag lisod ko og gamit sa technology na para ana na learning competencies" (Transcript 1, Page 2, Lines 12-16)

(I used Pebbles and bitaymax in delivering my lessons if I will find the technology to use is difficult and if there is no technology to use I just deliver the learning competencies)

When faced with technology constraints, seasoned secondary educators cultivate a resourceful culture by investigating alternative ways to offer learning competencies. When technology is unavailable or difficult to use, some teachers turn to tried-and-true methods like using boards, chalk, and locally made materials. Others use inventive instruments like bitaymax and pebbles for instruction. This adaptation highlights the value of ingenuity in education by ensuring successful instruction despite a range of technology limitations.

Innovative solutions in delivering lessons to the students. Use of offline learning materials such as textbook, workbooks, printed worksheets if the technology is not available. KII 9 said,

"We use offline learning materials sch as textbook, workbooks, printed worksheets, and other offliine materials that could use in delivering the lessons" (Transcript 9, Page 2, Line 40-42).

Seasoned secondary teachers also strategized to deliver lessons following the book. KII 1 said,

“diskarte lang dyud ko og pamaagi subayon ang lang naku unsa naa sa book og unsaon na siya” (Transcript 1, Page 1, Line 16-17). (strategize and find ways and follow what’s in the book on what to do)

Innovative activities without the use of technology on contextualized materials or activities. KII 5 said,

“Innovate activities without the use of technology or contextualize materials or activities. What is important is to deliver the learning competencies to the learners” (Transcript 5, Page 2, Line 36-37)

Seasoned secondary teachers find creative ways to meet technology constraints while still delivering instruction. When technology is not available, they make use of offline learning resources like printed worksheets, workbooks, and textbooks to maintain educational continuity. The transmission of learning competencies to students through contextualized materials and activities is prioritized by educators, who also carefully plan and adhere to book content while introducing creative, non-technological activities.

Seeking Help and Collaboration. Experienced Math teachers are frequently faced with the difficult challenge of incorporating technology into their lesson plans in the constantly changing realm of education. Even with their extensive expertise, these teachers understand that to successfully manage the challenges of integrating technology into the mathematics classroom, they must ask for assistance when needed and work together with other educators. To overcome obstacles and improve their students' learning experiences, seasoned educators should emphasize the value of teamwork and their readiness to ask for help from peers, IT specialists, and other experts. Experienced educators show their dedication to ongoing innovation and development in mathematics instruction by encouraging a collaborative environment and asking for assistance when necessary.

Seeking mentorship and guidance, LAC session every month provided by the LAC coordinator is one of the coping mechanisms by seasoned secondary teacher. KII 3 said,

“Through LAC sessions or focal group discussions. Asking colleagues who have varied ideas about technology” (Transcript 5, Page 3, Line 50-51).

Some seasoned secondary teachers ask support from colleagues every time they encounter difficulties on certain apps. KII 1 said,

“Nagapatabang ko sa akoang mga kauban labi na nay nalibgan sa paggamit sa technology para mahit dyud naku ang learning competencies.” (Transcript 1, Pages 1-2, Line 26-29).

(I ask support from my colleagues if I have some queries in my mind on how to use the technology for me to hit the learning competencies)

Other seasoned secondary teachers also shared some experiences in teaching mathematics seeking supports from our colleagues and experts by collaborations meetings and conference. KII 9 said,

“We seek support from our colleagues and experts by collaborations, meetings, and conferences. We even consult from our newly hired teachers with their expertise in information and communication technology (Transcript 9, Page 3, Line 60-62).

Seasoned secondary teachers use a variety of tactics to deal with the obstacles posed by technology, such as asking for help and mentoring through frequent LAC sessions and focus group talks. To take use of the knowledge of others—including recently hired teachers who are adept at information and communication technology—they also collaborate, meet, and attend conferences. They also depend on the assistance of their peers, especially when they are having problems with certain applications.

Seasoned teachers also recognize the need for assistance, tapping somebody who is expert technologically in doing. KII 11 said,

“I will tap somebody who are experts technologically in doing so but then as I have said I am limited only to those apps which I can only manipulate.” (Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 31-32).

Gathering some ideas on how to make a lesson easy and presentable also shared by the seasoned secondary teacher. KII 8 said,

“By the help of some media outfits, gathered some ideas on how to make the lesson easy and presentable with the use of the technology” (Transcript 8, Page 2, Line 26-27)

Asking questions to their IT whenever needed some help with technology one of the coping mechanisms by the seasoned Secondary teachers. KII 7 said,

“All our IT’s experts in our department were very accommodating so every time we encountered challenges in integrating technology in our math teaching we just ask for help” (Transcript 7 Page 3, Line 54-56)

Seasoned teachers understand the value of consulting technology specialists for help when faced with obstacles and rely on their knowledge to solve difficult problems. Additionally, they gather suggestions from a variety of sources, such as media organizations, to improve the way lessons are presented utilizing technology. They also gain from the assistance of IT specialists in their department, who are always willing to lend a hand when difficulties arising in incorporating technology into math instruction arise.

Asking their co-teachers for help repeatedly in times of the difficulties in using technology to overcome the changes in teaching mathematics. KII 1 said,

“dili dyud ko maulaw mangutana og balik balikon ginagamit dyud naku, mahadlok lang dyud ko pag naay mahilabtan basig mawala ang files” (Transcript 5, Page 2, Line 31-35).

(I am not ashamed to ask repeatedly my colleagues, I used it but sometimes I'm afraid if I will accidentally click files and it will be deleted)

In some ways, teachers also ask co-teachers on how to manipulate the technology. KII 11 said,

“Manawag lang ug kauban nga knowledgeable sa technology kay magpatabang kung unsaon na pag maniobra nga technology” (Transcript 11, Page 1, Line 12-13).

(I ask my co-teachers or those who are knowledgeable about technology to help me on how to use or manipulate the technology)

Other seasoned teachers asking assistance for their colleagues. KII 1 said,

“Through the assistance of my colleagues makalahutay ra pud sa pag gamit anang technology basta e approach og tarung sa mga kauban” (Transcript 1, Page 2, Line 25-26).

(through the assistance of my colleagues just to overcome how to use the technology and approach them nicely)

Seasoned teachers show a readiness to ask for assistance from their peers on a regular basis when they run into technological difficulties, highlighting the value of teamwork in getting things done. To successfully manage the challenges of integrating technology into mathematics instruction, they rely on the experience of their fellow educators. They also stress how important it is to treat coworkers with respect and candor to create a welcoming workplace that promotes learning and development.

Continuous Professional Development. As seasoned secondary teachers in teaching mathematics need to undergo professional development. They are never afraid to seek for assistance when it needed. KII 1 said,

“Hoy! Please tabangi ko kay dili naman ndyud ni maglihok, kay pagtuslok naku dili naman mugana, mag ampo sa dyud ko usa mag duol sa iyaha kay basig masuko kay naga balik-balik na biya ko og patabang niya” (Transcript 1, Page 1, Line 18-23)

(Hey, please help me it's not moving every time entered it it's not functioning, I pray that when approach her she will not be angry because I keep asking here repeatedly)

Having a peer tutoring sessions is another coping mechanism of the seasoned secondary teachers. KII 3 said,

“Through the help of my colleagues, we usually discuss it during LAC sessions. Mentoring each other to overcome the difficulties.” (Transcript 3, Page 2, Line 26-27)

Another coping mechanism of the seasoned secondary teachers is the need for ongoing professional development. KII 9 said,

“There are lots of trainings or professional development which seasoned teachers may undergo. It can be taken from a formal or informal settings. Formals settings such as conferences, course, seminars, webinars, and workshops, which we also undergo during the school year which also give us a good help.” (Transcript 9, Page 3, Line 46-50)

Seasoned secondary teachers stress the value of continued professional development, recognizing that to successfully incorporate technology into their math lessons, they must ask for help and continue learning. To improve their abilities and overcome obstacles when utilizing technology, they make use of peer tutoring sessions and take part in a variety of official and informal training opportunities, such as conferences, seminars, and workshops. Their proactive approach is indicative of their dedication to enhancing their pedagogical approaches and guaranteeing their students receive a top-notch education.

Fostering collaborative learning communities, requesting assistance from other educators and ongoing seminars. KII 8 said,

“Thru seminars and good camaraderie, every time we encounter difficulties on certain app. Our colleagues are very easy to approach for assistance.” (Transcript 8, Page 3, Line 56-57)

The help of the Master Teacher is one of the common coping mechanisms by the seasoned teachers in teaching mathematics. KII 15 said,

“Thru my master teacher gitagaan pud ko niya og help og input. We can easily tap easily our expert and he is ready all the time as long as we are open to anybody with regards to technology” (Transcript 15, Page 2, Line 43-46)

(Thru my master teacher, she give me an assistance and help and input. We can easily tap easily our expert and he is ready all the time as long as we are open to anybody with regards to technology)

Assistance from other educators with ICT knowledge was also shared by the seasoned Secondary Teachers in coping struggles in

technology. KII 9 said,

“We seek support from our colleagues and experts by collaboration meetings and conference. We even consult from our newly hired teachers with their expertise in information and communication technology” (Transcript 9, Page 3, Line 60-65)

Seasoned secondary teachers use teamwork techniques to overcome obstacles when teaching math with technology. They use the knowledge of newly employed educators with ICT skills and the experience of master teachers to seek support from peers during seminars and through camaraderie. This cooperative method creates a nurturing learning community wherein teachers may exchange ideas and get advice to improve their methods.

Building technological proficiency and confidence thru practice the applications two or three days before the discussion. KII 4 said,

“Every time, I get everything ready two to three days before the discussion because if I will prepare the materials a day before then tendency, I will forget the process on how to use the applications” (Transcript 4, Page 1, Line 32)

Doing some research in making lessons simplified, coping mechanisms of the seasoned secondary teachers. KII 6 said,

“By doing some research in making our lessons simplified and easy to understand to our students, as a teacher you need to find an alternative ways for you to deliver your competency” (Transcript 6, Page 2, Line 26-27)

Accessing the YouTube and watch online tutorial on how to use the applications is one of their coping mechanisms. KII 7 said,

“I watch video tutorials on how to use specific computer applications, sa kana na pamaagi mas makabalo pa me unsaon pag gamit sa technology or apps” (Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 32-33)

(I watch video tutorials on how to use specific computer applications, in that way I will learn more how to use the technology or apps)

Seasoned secondary teachers use a range of tactics to improve their technology literacy and self-assurance when instructing arithmetic. These include researching to make teaching simpler, practicing apps beforehand, and viewing online tutorials on websites like YouTube to learn how to use technology and programs efficiently. Teachers might feel more equipped and capable when incorporating technology into their lessons thanks to these proactive measures.

Experienced secondary math teachers use a variety of coping mechanisms to improve their techniques despite the many obstacles they face while incorporating technology into their lessons. Prioritizing ongoing education and teamwork, they are dedicated to staying up to date with technology developments to enhance the educational experiences of their students. These teachers have a lifetime learning stance that incorporates strategic planning, independent study, and drawing on the knowledge of family members and peers. Their growth mentality and proactive approach to professional development highlight their commitment to enhancing their technology-assisted teaching methods.

These seasoned educators also show resiliency and inventiveness in overcoming technical obstacles. They look for creative solutions on their own initiative and adjust to overcome obstacles by working with IT experts or making use of existing resources. The foundation of their classrooms' effective technology integration is this cooperative and supportive atmosphere. In the face of changing educational technologies, these educators make sure their teaching practices stay dynamic and effective by remaining flexible and being willing to go back to old approaches when needed. Their ability to bounce back from setbacks, solve problems creatively, and strive for constant progress emphasizes how important they are to the advancement of math education and getting kids ready for the digital age.

Forms of support needed by the seasoned secondary teachers in teaching mathematics in using technology from the school administration.

Seasoned secondary teachers frequently need comprehensive assistance from school administrators to successfully negotiate the challenges of incorporating technology into their pedagogical methods when it comes to teaching mathematics. Support comes in many forms, such as having access to sufficient technology resources, opportunities for professional development specifically focused on technology integration, and administrative guidelines that create an atmosphere that is favorable for experimenting and innovating with educational technology. These forms of support needed by the seasoned secondary teacher can be grouped into four emerging themes: Professional Development and Learning Opportunities, sharing experience and peer collaboration, resource allocation and infrastructure support, and building healthy relationships with stakeholders. That can be shown in Table 3.

Table 3. *Thematic Map of the forms of support needed by the seasoned secondary teachers in teaching mathematics in using technology from the school administration*

<i>First Theme:</i>	<i>Second Theme:</i>
<i>Professional Development and Learning Opportunities</i>	<i>Sharing Experience and Peer Collaboration</i>
Access to relevant Professional Development	Peer Mentorship and Coaching
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impart struggles and suggestions for solutions from our peers from these gatherings. Conducting trainings and workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ask colleagues who have varied ideas about technology. Easy to approach colleagues.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • INSET applications of mathematical apps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration meetings and conferences.
Pedagogical Training for Technology Integration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classes where technology integration was taking place and to ask questions. • Training or professional development • Training that enhances knowledge of us seasoned teacher. 	Formalized Collaborative Structures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal settings as conferences, course, seminars, webinars, and workshops • Seminars and good camaraderie • There are indeed those who ask during the LAC sessions.
Availability of Timely and Ongoing Support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aids in the improvement of our methods and strategies • Workshop training to cope with the trends of our students. • Create lessons that are applicable/entertaining to the new trend students. 	Informal Knowledge Sharing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch video lectures to hone their classroom management techniques. • Easily tap experts regarding technology. • Colleagues are very easy to approach.
Third Theme: Resource Allocation and Infrastructure Support	Fourth Theme: Building Healthy Relationships with Stakeholders
Limited Fundings for technology resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allotted a portion of the MOOE to purchase materials needed for classroom instructions. • Taking appropriate measures to establish and maintain electricity in the classroom. • The need for materials in the classrooms. 	Building relationship with the Administrator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting trainings and seminars • Webinars and INSET given by the department heads. • Workshops, special courses offered online, mentoring, modeling
Lack of technical support and training <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Request with regards with the materials needed cannot provide by the government • Back to basics localizations and contextualization approach • Being resourceful and researching with youtube 	Engagement with parents and Guardians <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tapping some school stakeholders supports financially. • Approach and tap some parents for assistance. • Supply loads and provide quality phones to their child.
Building a Supportive School Culture <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts offer technological updates. • Master Teachers offers aid from the seasoned teachers. • Teachers who are willing to help the seasoned teachers 	Collaborative Partnership with colleagues <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • asking during the LAC sessions • help from our department IT experts. • occasionally went to see my colleagues' classes where technology integration was taking place and to ask questions.

Professional Development and Learning Opportunities. As the field of mathematics education changes constantly, experienced teachers look for ways to improve their pedagogical techniques, especially when it comes to using technology in the classroom. The need of continuous professional development for experienced teachers is explored in this introduction, emphasizing the need for them to take the initiative to keep up with new developments in technology and creative teaching techniques. These educators engage in lifelong learning to effectively use technology in the mathematics classroom through workshops, training sessions, and cooperative efforts. Experienced educators who take advantage of professional development opportunities enable themselves to create dynamic classrooms that encourage student participation, critical thinking, and mathematical ability.

Access to relevant professional development and learning opportunities, impart struggles and suggestions for solutions from our peers from these gatherings. KII 4 said,

“We seasoned teachers can impart struggles and ask suggestions for solutions from our peers from these gatherings, from this we learned not just only from the speakers but also to those people who attended seminars naa me makutlo pud sa ilaha na makatabang sa amoa pagkabalo” (Transcript 12, Page 2, Line 46-50)

(We seasoned teachers can impart struggles and ask suggestions for solutions from our peers from these gatherings, from this we learned not just only from the speakers but also to those people who attended seminars we will have learnings from them that can help us)

Conducting trainings and workshops by the division was one of the Supports received from the division to the seasoned secondary teachers. KII 7 said,

“Conducting trainings and workshops. Alloted portion of the MOOE to purchase materials needed for classroom instructions” (Transcript 7, Page 3, Line 43-44)

Some seasoned teachers also added an INSET applications of mathematical apps are one of the supports from the administration. KII 1 said,

“INSET application of different mathematical application parehas anang exegegebra, desmos og uban pa” (Transcript 1, Page 2, Line 32-33).

(INSET application of different mathematical applications like exegegebra, desmos and other apps)

The school administration's pertinent professional development opportunities and workshops, which allow seasoned secondary teachers to share challenges and look to their peers for solutions, are very beneficial. The administration's assistance also includes trainings, funding for instructional materials, and the implementation of in-service training (INSET) courses on mathematical applications. These programs improve the ability of educators to use technology to provide math lessons in an efficient manner.

Pedagogical training for technology integration, particularly training that enhances knowledge of us seasoned teachers. KII 8 a seasoned secondary teacher said,

“Training that would enhances knowledge of us seasoned teachers to create lessons that is applicable entertaining to the new trend to students. They also provide technical assistance to us teachers who need help specially during the pandemic that we are not good in using technology in delivering our lessons in mathematics. During those time we are the one that really needs to have a big adjustment” (Transcript 8, Page 3, Line 41-46).

Seasoned Secondary teachers provide a lot of trainings or professional development that could be a formal or informal seminars. KII 9 said,

“There are lots of trainings or professional development which us seasoned teachers may undergo. Pwede ra pinamaagi sa formal or informal settings. Formal settings such as conferences, courses, seminars, webinars, and workshops, na maagian namu sa eskwelahan taga tuig na makatabang dyud sa amoa” (Transcript 9, Page 3, Line 46-50).

(There are lots of trainings or professional development which us seasoned teachers may undergo. It can be taken in formal or informal settings. Formal settings such as conferences, courses, seminars, webinars, and workshops, which we also undergo during the school year which also give us a good help)

Teacher also visits classes where technology integration took place, was one of the forms of supports from them. KII 4 said,

“I occasionally went to see my colleagues where technology integration was taking place and to ask questions. This aids in the improvement of our methods and strategies.” (Transcript 4, Page 2, Line 49-51)

It emphasizes the value of pedagogical training for seasoned secondary teachers integrating technology to improve their expertise in designing captivating classes. These workshops, which come in a variety of forms, such as official conferences and casual get-togethers, offer instructors invaluable assistance as they navigate the difficulties of incorporating technology into math education. Furthermore, assistance from peers who are already skilled in integrating technology into the classroom is a great way to exchange best practices and enhance instructional techniques.

Availability of timely and ongoing support specially in workshop training to cope with the trend of our students. KII 6 said,

“workshops and training to cope up the trends of our students para makasabay pud me sa mga estudyante mao na ilahang gina provide sa amoa” (Transcript 6, Page 1, Line 34-35)

(workshops and training to cope up the trends of our students for us to be along with the students those are the seminars they provided)

Create lessons that are applicable and entertaining to the new trends of the students. KII 8 said,

“Training that would enhance knowledge of a seasoned teachers to create lessons that is applicable and entertaining to the new trend students” (Transcript 8, Page 2, Line 41-42)

Technical assistance was provided by the seasoned teachers by the administrator. KII 5 said,

“Nagahatag sad sila og technical support sa amoa mga maestra na nanginahanglan og tabang labi na katong pandemic na dili me kabalo mo gamit sa technology sa pagdeliver sa amoang lesson sa math.” (Transcript 3, Page 3, Line 43-45)

(They also provided technical assistance to us teachers who needs help especially during the pandemic that we are not good in using technology in delivering our lessons in mathematics)

It underscores the significance of prompt and continuous support, especially in the form of seminars and training sessions, to assist experienced educators in keeping abreast of student developments and proficiently using technology into their teaching. By making these efforts, we hope to keep teachings interesting and relevant for students. Furthermore, administrators' technical support helps teachers overcome obstacles associated with integrating technology, particularly in times of pandemics.

Sharing Experience and Peer Collaboration. Seasoned math teachers frequently turn to the strength of peer support and collaboration while navigating the use of technology into their lesson plans. To improve student learning results, this introduction looks at how seasoned teachers can pool their knowledge and share their experiences. Working together with other experienced educators, teachers can learn about useful technology resources and approaches to teaching mathematics. By working together, they create a supportive professional community committed to ongoing progress through meaningful exchanges of concepts, best practices, and creative solutions. The significance of group expertise in fostering instructional innovation and student achievement in mathematics education is highlighted by this emphasis on experience sharing and peer collaboration.

Peer mentorship and coaching is one of the supports from the administrator that the seasoned secondary teachers got by asking colleagues who have varied ideas about technology. As what KII 5 said,

“Asking my colleagues who have varied ideas about technology sir, magduol dyud me sa ilaha or sila nagahatag pud sila og tabang sa amoa pamaagi sa LAC sessions namu tapos naga groupings me para matudluan dyud. (Transcript 5, Page 3, Line 51-52).

(Asking my colleagues who have varied ideas about technology sir, I will come to them, or they will also give us help in our method in our LAC sessions and then groupings for me to teach you.)

Some seasoned secondary shared also experience about their colleagues that easy to approach. KII 8 said,

“Thru seminar and good camaraderie, everytime we encounter difficulties on certain apps, our colleagues are very easy to approach.” (Transcript 8, Page 3, Line 56-57).

They also shared that collaborative and conference meeting is one of the supports they received from the administrator. KII 9 said,

“We seek support from our colleagues and experts by collaboration meeting and conferences, naa me mga kauban nagrabe dyud mutabang sa amoa pag naa me need sa ilaha. Kabalo man sila sa amoa na mag liusod dyud me sa technology” (Transcript 9, Page 3, Line 60-61).

(We seek support from our colleagues and experts by collaboration meeting and conferences, I have colleagues who help us when we need them. They also know that we have a hard time with technology)

It emphasizes the value of peer coaching and mentoring from peers with different perspectives on technology, especially in LAC sessions and cooperative groups. It also emphasizes how approachable and encouraging coworkers are, always willing to help when facing challenges with apps. Furthermore, cooperative gatherings and conferences are excellent venues for getting advice and assistance from peers and professionals, particularly when it comes to resolving issues pertaining to technology integration.

Formalized collaborative structures, by formal settings as conferences, course, seminars, webinars by workshops are some of the forms of supports of seasoned teachers. KII 9 also shared some experiences,

“There are lots of trainings or professionals development which seasoned teachers may undergo. It can be taken from a formal or informal settings. Formal settings such as conferences, course, seminars, webinars, and workshops, na maagian namu sa eskwelahan taga tuig na makatabang dyud sa amoa” (Transcript 9, Page 3, Line 46-50)”

(There are lots of trainings or professional development which us seasoned teachers may undergo. It can be taken in formal or informal settings. Formal settings such as conferences, courses, seminars, webinars, and workshops, which we also undergo during the school year which also give us a good help)

Thru Seminars and good camaraderie are one of the forms of supports from the administrator. KII 6 said,

“daghan kayo ginahatag sila na assistance sa amoa sir labi napag makabalo ang amoang head na naglisod me ana unsaon pag gamit, naa dayun me kauban an mag tabang sa amoa kanang newly hired teacher mo duol sa amoa para tabangan me nila.” (Transcript 6, Page 3, Line 56-58)

(You give us a lot of assistance, sir, especially when our head found out that it was difficult for me how to use it, I was there with someone who would help us, that newly hired teacher near us to help me.)

Seasoned secondary teachers are also asking during LAC sessions. KII 13 said,

“Nagapangutana dyud ko sa mga bagohan namu sir og labi na pag abot sa LAC session namu kay para makabalo dyud ko og taman ana na technology” (Transcript 13, Page 2, Line 49)

(I am asking our newbies, sir, especially when it comes to our LAC session, because I want to know about that technology.)

The value of organized collaboration structures including webinars, conferences, courses, seminars, and workshops, which offer experienced teachers' beneficial opportunities for professional growth who also emphasized. Furthermore, the assistance provided by administrators—exemplified by their seminars and cooperative spirit—is crucial in resolving issues pertaining to the integration of technology. Furthermore, the proactive participation of experienced educators in requesting support, especially during LAC sessions,

indicates their dedication to improving their technological competence.

Informal Knowledge sharing, watching watch video lecturer to hone their classroom management techniques were also the forms of support by the administrator. KII 7 said,

“ginapatan-aw me og video tutorials na ginapasa sa amoang head para mas makabalo pa mi anang technology og unsaon pag gamit sa computer applications” (Transcript 7, Page 2, Line 32-33)

(They let me watch video tutorials that are passed on to our heads so that we can know more about that technology and how to use it in computer applications)

Secondary seasoned teachers easily tap their experts regarding technology. KII 11 said,

“We can tap easily our expert and he is ready all the time as long as we are open to anybody with regards to technology” (Transcript 11, Page 2, Line 62-63)

Another informal knowledge sharing by the seasoned secondary teachers is tapping their colleague. KII 8 said,

“Our colleagues are very easy to approach, mura namu sila og mga anak unya kami ang ilahang inahan na nag lisod og gamit sa technology na nagpatabang” (Transcript 8, Page 3, Line 57-58)

(Our colleagues are very easy to approach, they are like our children then we are their mothers who are having difficulty using technology to help)

It emphasizes how crucial it is for seasoned secondary teachers to share informal knowledge to improve their technological competency. This includes exercises like seeing video lessons that their supervisors have suggested to enhance their comprehension of computers and technology. Their learning process for incorporating technology into their teaching methods is further facilitated by having easy access to professionals and colleagues who are eager to help and support them.

Resource Allocation and Infrastructure Support. When it comes to using technology to teach mathematics, experienced teachers frequently struggle with infrastructure support and resource allocation. This introduction explores the vital role that sufficient infrastructure and resources play in enabling successful integration of technology in mathematics instruction. Securing current gadgets, software, and technical assistance are among the resources that seasoned educators must secure to improve their teaching approaches. They also depend on educational officials and school administrators to provide strong infrastructure support, such as dependable internet connectivity, modern technology, and comfortable learning settings. For seasoned educators, however, overcoming resource limitations and campaigning for infrastructural upgrades can present formidable challenges. Despite these obstacles, their adaptability and resourcefulness allow them to innovate and adjust, making the most of the resources at hand to enhance the educational experiences of their pupils. This introduction clarifies the intricate relationships that exist between infrastructure support, resource allocation, and successful technology integration in mathematics education. It emphasizes the significance of resolving these relationships to enable seasoned educators to succeed in their teaching attempts.

Resources allocation and Infrastructure, particularly to the limited fundings for technology resources and allotted a portion of the MOOE of conducting trainings. KII 7 said,

“Conducting trainings and workshops. Allotted a portion of the MOOE to purchase materials needed for classroom instructions” (Transcript 7, Page 3, Line 43-44).

Secondary Seasoned Teachers also shared the supports they wanted to particularly the need for materials in the classroom. KII 3 said,

“First, we need to have a projector, television, sound system, and most especially mathematics manipulative materials inside the classroom, kay wala dyud kayo me materials na gamiton unsaon mana pagtudlo sa amoang mga kaubanan kung wala gihapon me mga gamit.” (Transcript 3, Page 2, Line 38-39).

(First, we need to have a projector, television, sound system, and most especially mathematics manipulative materials inside the classroom, because you don't have materials to use, how can our colleagues teach us if we still don't have materials.)

Taking appropriate measures to establish and maintain electricity also shared by the seasoned secondary teacher. KII 13 said,

“The administration must help me by taking appropriate measures to establish and maintain electricity in each classroom” (Transcript 13, Page 2, Line 46-47)

Underlines how crucial it is to provide infrastructural assistance and resource allocation for experienced secondary instructors who want to integrate technology. As KII 7 points out, this includes financing for training sessions and the acquisition of supplies needed for in-class instruction. To support effective instruction, KII 3 also highlights the necessity of basic equipment such projectors, televisions, and manipulative materials for mathematics. In addition, KII 13 highlights how important it is to have steady electricity in classrooms to facilitate the usage of technology.

Lack of technical support and training of seasoned secondary teachers results to going back to basics localizations and contextualization approach. KII 2 said,

“We use differentiated instruction where some groups utilize technology while others have differentiated task. Most of the time, I go back to basics localization and contextualization approach” (Transcript 2, Page 3, Line 51-53).

It was also emphasized by our seasoned secondary teachers utilize technology while others have different task. KII 3 said,

“Ang amoang ginabuhay sir, kay ginagamit namu ang ubang technology na available since dili man tanan makagamit ang ubang ginabuhay nila kay mag buhat lang og lain na task.” (Transcript 3, Page 2 Line 34-36).

(What we are doing, sir, is because we have limited technology that is available since not everyone can use what others are doing because they are just doing another task.)

Being resourceful and researching with the use of YouTube. KII 1 said,

“Mag search lang ko sa youtube kay daghna man makuha didto since dili man tanan maka apil sa seminar kay limited lang man slot og budget” (Transcript 1, Page 3, Line 47-48)

(I'll just search on YouTube because there's a lot to be found there since not everyone can join the seminar because there's only a limited slot and budget.)

Seasoned secondary teachers resort to simple localization and contextualization techniques in their instruction due to a lack of technical support and training. As noted by KII 2 and KII 3, some educators turn to differentiated education, in which some groups use technology and others are given distinct assignments. Furthermore, as mentioned by KII 1, teachers must be imaginative to make up for limited seminar participation due to funding and slot restrictions, thus they search YouTube.

Building a supportive school culture where experts offer technological updates to the seasoned secondary teachers. KII 11 said,

“Naa me experts sa amoang department nga naga offer sa amoa nga mag-update s technology” (Transcript 11, Page 2, Line 50-51)

(We have experts in our department who offer us help and to update the new technology)

Master Teachers offers aid from seasoned teachers as a form of support from the administrator. KII 15 said,

“Thru master teacher gitagaan pod ko niya og help og input. We can tap easily our expert and he is ready all the time as long as we are open to anybody with regards to technology” (Transcript 15, Page 2, Line 43-45)

(Thru master teacher He also gave me help and input. We can tap easily our expert and he is ready all the time as long as we are open to anybody with regards to technology)

Teachers who are willing to help the seasoned teachers was also shared by the seasoned secondary teachers in teaching mathematics. KII 8 said,

“Our colleagues are very easy to approach pag naa kay kailangan tabangan dayun ka pasalamat pud kayo ko naa me kauban na ing ana” (Transcript 8, Page 3, Line 57-58)

(Our colleagues are very easy to approach If you need help, our colleagues are always with you, and we are grateful about it)

It captures the significance of a welcoming school culture in giving seasoned secondary teachers access to technology updates and support. As KII 11 emphasizes, department experts provide support for technical improvements. As highlighted by KII 15, master teachers also have a significant role to play in supporting and advising more experienced educators. Additionally, as mentioned by KII 8, a collaborative environment is fostered by coworkers who are willing to help.

Building a Healthy Relationship. Improving the way technology is integrated into mathematics instruction requires fostering positive relationships between experienced educators and other stakeholders. To build a supportive atmosphere for effective teaching and learning, this introduction examines the importance of fostering strong connections among teachers, administrators, students, and parents. To successfully negotiate the challenges of incorporating technology into mathematics instruction, seasoned educators understand the value of teamwork and communication with peers, administrators, and educational support personnel. Furthermore, building rapport and trust with students promotes active participation and creates a positive learning environment in which technology may be easily incorporated into mathematical ideas. Keeping the lines of communication open with parents and guardians also guarantees their support and involvement in their children's educational path, which includes utilizing technology to teach mathematics. Experienced educators who put a high priority on developing relationships can create a network of support that helps instructors and students alike benefit from the successful incorporation of technology in mathematics instruction.

Building relationships with the administrator thru conducting trainings and seminars are one of the supports from the administrator to the seasoned secondary teachers. KII 12 said,

“Conducting trainings and seminars. Mao gina provide sa amoa sir, naay seminar pero dili lang dyud tanan maka apil sa mga seminars kay limited raman gud mag depende sa allocation sa MOOE” (Transcript 12, Page 2, Line 55-61).

(Conducting trainings and seminars. That is what they provide sir, there is a seminar but not everyone can participate in the seminars because it is limited depending on the allocation of MOOE)

Added also by the seasoned secondary teachers about webinars and INSET given by the department heads. KII 2 said,

“Webinars INSET given by the department IT, free internet in the department but not all classroom” (Transcript 2, Page 3, Line 47-48).

Workshops, special course offered online, mentoring modelling was given to seasoned secondary teachers. KII 5 shared also it experienced,

“Workshops, special courses offered online, mentoring, modelling, those are seminars that offered from our department head” (Transcript 5, Page 3, Line 41).

Administrators assist seasoned secondary teachers in several ways, including as seminars and training sessions, as KII 12 emphasizes. Nonetheless, participation restrictions brought about by financial constraints are recognized. KII 2 further said that department heads' webinars and in-service training (INSET) as well as free internet access provide additional opportunities for professional growth. Moreover, as stressed by KII 5, workshops, unique online courses, mentoring, and modeling opportunities all support experienced instructors' professional development.

Engagement with parents and Guardians by tapping some school stakeholders support financially. KII 13 said,

“Akoang ginabuhay sir pag naay need dyud sa classroom parehas anang HDMI akoang gina tap ang mga ginikanan sa akoang mga bata kay dili man pud ni amoa para man pud ni sa ilahang anak” (Transcript 13, Page 2, Line 58-59)

(What I do it, sir, when there is a need in the classroom, it's the same HDMI that I tap the parents of my children because it's not ours, it's also for their children.)

Added by the seasoned secondary teachers is to approach and tap some parent's assistance. KII 11 said,

“Akoang ginabuhay sir kay sugod palang sa klase nagapatawag ko sa meeting akoang gina ingun sa ginikanan ang mga kulang na need sa classroom labi na magamit sa amoa klase unya mo suporta man pud mga ginikanan sir basta open lang dyud ka sa unsay need sa klase” (Transcript 11, Page 2, Line 56-59)

(What I'm doing, sir, is that from the beginning of the class, I'm calling the meeting, I'm telling the parents about the things that are missing in the classroom, especially if they can be used in our class, then you can also support the parents, sir, as long as you're open to what the class needs.)

Seasoned secondary teachers also share about supply loads and provide quality phone to their child. KII 10 said,

“katong panahon sa pandemic sir kay ang government man nag hatag og tablet para mapagamit sa mga bata, akoang ginabuhay ato sir kay nag inform pud ko sa mga ginikanan na sila na bahala sa load para maka access sila sa mga activity sa mga bata na gamit ang tablet, dayun karun naa man me mga activity na pwede mag gamit og cellphone ang mga ginikanan nag provide og cellphone sa ilahang anak para magamit sa klase” (Transcript 10, Page 3, Line 54-60)

(during the pandemic, sir, because the government also gave tablets for the children to use, I am doing it, sir, because I also informed the parents that they will take care of the load so that they can access the activities of the children using the tablet, then now we have activities where parents can use cellphones to provide cellphones for their children to use in class)

Proficiency secondary educators actively include parents and guardians by requesting their financial assistance for necessary teaching supplies. As KII 13 pointed out, this involves utilizing the resources of school stakeholders. For example, KII 13 uses HDMI cables that parents donate for use in the classroom. Furthermore, KII 11 stresses the value of having open lines of contact with parents and setting up meetings to talk about the requirements of the classroom and get support from them. Additionally, KII 10 describes actions taken during the pandemic to support learning. For example, parents were notified that they could load government-issued tablets and even provide cellphones for their kids to use in class. This illustrates how teachers and parents worked together to support learning.

Collaborative partnership with colleagues thru asking during the LAC session. KII 13 said,

“Naga pangutana dyud sa bago og LAC session mao na akoang ginabuhay sir wala ko naga pa alig-alig na kabalo dyud pag nalisdan ko ana during LAC session mangutana dyud ko” (Transcript 13, Page 2, Line 49)

(I'd asked a question to our newly hired and during our LAC session that's what I do If I find it difficult specially during the LAC session)

Seasoned secondary teachers also share about help from our department IT experts. KII 7 said,

"All our IT experts in our department were very accommodating so every time we encountered challenges in integrating technology in our math teaching we just ask for help" (Transcript 7, Page 3, Line 54-56)

Occasionally they went to see their colleagues' classes where technology integration was taking place and to ask questions was share by the seasoned secondary teacher. KII 4 said,

"Occasionally went to see my colleagues' classes where technology integration was taking place and to ask questions. This aides in the improvement of our methods and strategies" (Transcript 4, Page 2, Line 49-51)

Seasoned secondary teachers rely on cooperative collaborations and look for outside assistance to improve their technology-based teaching strategies. As KII 13 pointed out, this entails actively participating in LAC sessions to share experiences and ask questions. Furthermore, as KII 7 emphasizes, students gain from support given by department IT specialists. Additionally, as stressed by KII 4, they participate in informal knowledge-sharing by going to classes taught by colleagues where technology integration is being used. This facilitates the sharing of ideas and the development of instructional methodologies.

For seasoned secondary teachers to effectively integrate technology into mathematics instruction, school administration support is essential. Highlighting the value of peer collaboration, professional development, resource distribution, and fostering positive relationships within the school community are the kinds of support that the participants mentioned.

It becomes clear that professional development is an essential component of assistance, and that workshops, training sessions, and educational opportunities are critical in helping instructors become more technologically proficient. Seasoned teachers may keep up with the latest developments in technology and pedagogy by actively participating in continuous learning and exchanging experiences with colleagues. This will enhance their teaching methods and improve student outcomes.

To build a friendly professional environment where educators can share ideas, tactics, and best practices, peer collaboration and experience sharing are equally important. Teachers can overcome obstacles and benefit from one another's experience to improve technology integration in mathematics classrooms by combining their resources and knowledge.

Furthermore, infrastructural support and sufficient resource allocation are essential for a successful technological integration. For educators to successfully use technology in teaching mathematics, they must first get the resources they need, such as up-to-date devices, software, and technical support. To support teachers' efforts to integrate technology into their lectures, school administrations must prioritize infrastructure improvements, making sure that there is current technology, dependable internet connectivity, and appropriate learning spaces.

Ultimately, fostering positive relationships among stakeholders is crucial to establishing a welcoming environment that promotes efficient instruction and learning. Experienced educators may successfully integrate technology into mathematics instruction by building excellent relationships with administrators, parents, students, and colleagues. This will help them obtain the support and cooperation they need.

In conclusion, school administrators can enable seasoned secondary teachers to successfully navigate the challenges of technology integration in mathematics education by offering comprehensive support that includes professional development, peer collaboration, resource allocation, and relationship-building. Teachers can develop dynamic classrooms that encourage student engagement, critical thinking, and mathematical competency in an increasingly digital environment by working together and committing to continuous improvement.

Conclusions

As a public-school teacher who studied Master of Arts in Teaching Mathematics discovered the different struggles and coping mechanisms of the Seasoned Secondary teachers in teaching mathematics using technology during conducting my studies. Seasoned teacher in mathematics faces different problems during integrating technology in delivering the lessons to the learners trying to meet the characteristics of the 21st century teachers.

The research emphasizes the significant challenges experienced by seasoned secondary math educators in incorporating technology into their lessons. Technological difficulties, technological resources constrain, resistance to change, and curriculum integration are notable obstacles. Teachers' attitudes, backgrounds, and the quickly changing digital environment are all factors in these obstacles. To tackle these obstacles, a thorough approach comprising infrastructure enhancements, continual assistance, and professional development is needed. The study reveals a nuanced interaction of challenges, coping strategies, and sources of support among seasoned secondary educators negotiating the use of technology in math instruction. The theoretical underpinnings offer a thorough framework for comprehending and resolving the difficulties educators encounter in this dynamic educational environment.

The study sheds light on the many and interrelated difficulties experienced secondary math teachers encounter when incorporating technology into their lesson plans. These problems require a comprehensive approach to solve and include familiarity with established ways, resistance to change, outdated equipment, and technological hurdles. To overcome these obstacles and continue providing high-quality instruction, instructors also use coping strategies include flexibility, problem-solving techniques, constant learning, and asking

for assistance. To help teachers overcome challenges and improve their teaching practices, school administration support—which includes professional development, peer collaboration, resource allocation, and stakeholder relationship-building—is essential. I’ve also realized that seasoned teachers are willing to adapt changes been provided some possible assistance that helped them coping up some problems in integrating technology in teaching mathematics but one of the problems that occurs is the readiness of the public school of having a facility to be used. In the end, overcoming these obstacles calls for cooperation between educators, managers, legislators, and other interested parties to establish an atmosphere that supports efficient technology integration and enriched learning opportunities for math students.

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